

Machine Translation System for Numeral in English Text to Yorùbá Language

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Abstract—The machine translation of numbers from the English language into the Yorùbá language is an integral part of a machine translation system from the English language into the Yorùbá language as a numeral system is an important aspect of any language. This paper presents a computational approach to English number text translation into Yorùbá text. The approach shows the number of ways an English number text can be translated into the Yorùbá language and the various forms in which the translations can be done based on context. This was carried out by collecting numeral data from the Yorùbá literature, formulating context-free grammar, and implementing the model with the Python programming language. The evaluation of the system was carried out using the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) score. The result of the approach is a software artefact for translating number text in the context of simple English sentences to Yorùbá text. They can further be integrated as a module into a robust machine translation system for effective and accurate translation from the English language to the Yorùbá language.

Keywords—number, machine translation, computation, Yoruba

I. INTRODUCTION

Direct machine translation from the English language to the Yorùbá language is an upcoming research area. Some research works like [1, 4, 5, 8, 9, 16, 17, 18, 19, 31] have looked in different ways of translating text from the English language to the Yorùbá language. Few works that have been done on the numerals and their direct machine translation of numerals to *Igbo* language [28] and Yorùbá language are [6,7,15]. However, these are done in isolation and not in context. Addressing the translation of numbers in isolation to Yorùbá is not sufficient to solve the challenge of machine translation from English to the Yorùbá language since the Yorùbá language has a different use of numbers based on context.

This work addresses the machine translation of numbers in the context of English phrases to the corresponding Yorùbá phrase. Yorùbá phrases in the context of this work are constructed using the

standard Yorùbá way of writing, which is the Latin script.

A numeral is an integral part of a language and numeral translation is an important aspect of machine translation. Yorùbá is spoken as the first language in states like Èkiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo Òsun, and Òyó. of Nigeria. It is also spoken in some areas in Kogi and Kwara states of Nigeria [32].

The Yorùbá numeral is an outstanding numeral system among the world's numeral systems. One peculiar issue is over-counting, and another is that it cascades three number bases: base five, ten, and twenty. Unlike some numeral systems around the world, the Yorùbá numeral has different forms of usage. These are cardinal, ordinal, adverb of number, adverb of time, adjectival, and all-form [3,24,30]. Number text in the English language can be translated into these various forms based on the context in which they appear. This paper presents the machine translation of English number text in the context of English Noun and Verb phrases. This section is followed the literature review, methodology, result, and conclusion.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for translation occurs when people don't understand the medium of communication. The need arises for a translator (a person who understands both the source and target language) to translate the language of communication to the language of the listener who doesn't understand the language of communication. According to [25], translation helps people overcome linguistic and cultural barriers. To take away this barrier automatically, the need for translating with the computer comes into play. Machine Translation is the process of obtaining the target language text from the source text through automatic means.

It is a multidisciplinary field with approaches from both linguistics and statistics [14]. There are some approaches to machine translation. Direct translation [35], Rule-Based Machine Translation [2], Corpus-based translation [26,34], Knowledge-base translation [33].

There are Hybrid approaches to machine translation, such as Word-based models [11],

Phrase-based models [29], Syntax based models [20], and Forest-Based Translation [27]. This work adopts the rule-based machine translation approach because the *Yorùbá* language is low-resource. This work adopts the linguistic approach (usage of grammar).

Number an abstract entity that forms an integral part of a language and the degree of development of a language is determined by how complex its numeral system is [36]. *Yorùbá* numeral as a system of numbers is a complex system that cascaded three number bases: five (quinary), ten (decimal), and twenty (vigesimal).

A. Forms of *Yorùbá* number

The *Yorùbá* number system has different forms of representation for usage. [3] enumerates five forms which are Long-form, e.g., eéjì short form èjì, Adjectival form méjì and ordinal form èkejì for the number two. [30] enumerates the cardinal, ordinal, adjectives, adverbs, adverbs in the form of once, twice, money, time, etc. [24] classified *Yorùbá* numerals into two main groups, namely, cardinal and ordinal (which is otherwise called serial). The cardinal was said to be in five forms: simple enumeration, numeral adjectives, numismatics, adverb of number, and adverb of time. The forms considered in the paper are shown in Table I.

B. Phrase structure grammar

A phrase structure grammar is introduced by Noam Chomsky in his work, [12] is a term used to define phrase structure rules, a type of rewrite rule used to describe the syntax of a given language. These grammars are also known as constituency grammars.

A phrase is a grammar of how phrases are formed. The phrases can be any verb phrase (VP) whose head is a verb, noun phrase (NP) whose head is a verb, or prepositional phrase (PP) whose head is a preposition [21].

1) X-Bar Theory for parse tree generation

X-bar theory, first proposed by [13], is the theory of syntactic category formation. It has two claims:

1. phrase may contain intermediate constituents' projection from a head (X).
2. the system of the projected category may be more than one category, e.g., Noun (N), Verb (V), Adjective (A), Preposition (P), etc.

The letter X is used arbitrarily to represent a part of speech, e.g. (V, N, A, P). At the phrasal level, XP is used to represent the lexical phrase.

The theory was incorporated into transformational and non-transformational theories of syntax, which include Government and binding theory (GB), Generalised Phrase Structure Grammar (GPSG), Lexical Functional Grammar

(LFG) and Head-driven phrase structure grammar (HPSG). X-bar is the theory of how phrases are formed. In an X phrase, we have an optional specifier and an X-bar in any other, a kind of X-bar consisting of an X-bar and an adjunct, another type of X-bar consisting of an X which is the head and any number of compliments. In the traditional phrase structure rule,

$$S \rightarrow NP VP \quad (1)$$

but according to [10], the X-bar theory reanalyse this rule by determining the sentence's head, complement, and specifier. Neither the two sides of the rule in Equation 1 can be the head of the sentence because they are phrases themselves. Therefore the rule is not referred to as a sentence (S) in X-bar theory but as an Inflectional Phrase (IP). The NP becomes the specifier, while the VP, the sentence's predicate, is the IP's complement. Figure 1 shows the schema for forming the parse tree for the X-bar theory. X-bar theory is better than other phrase structure grammar theories because it can be used in a bigger unit. We can make clear ambiguity and can use it in many different languages. *Yorùbá* sentences can have deep structures because the number in the sentence itself can be broken down into their grammar.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection and Analysis

The sentences with a number and their corresponding translations were extracted from [3, 24,30]. [30] gives the context in which number text can occur in the English language and the corresponding form the number text takes in the *Yorùbá* language.

The process of translation involves the following:

1. When the number is preceded by the word "the", "all", a possessive noun, or a possessive pronoun followed by a noun as shown in the0020examples below, it is translated into the all-form equivalent.
 - The five eggs → *Àwọn ẹyìn mǎràrún-ún*
 - All three → *Àwọn méjèṣta*.
 - Mayowa's seven oranges → *Ọsàn Mǎyòwà méjèje*

TABLE I: FORMS OF YORUBA AND THE CORRESPONDING NUMBERS

NO.	Adjective	Adverb of Number	of	Adverb of Time	All-form
one	òkan	òkòòkan		èèkan	-
two	méjì	méjíméjì		èèméjì	méjèèjì
three	méta	métaméta		èèméta	métèèta
four	mérin	mérinmérin		èèmérin	mérèèrin
five	márùn-ún	márúnmárún		èèmárún	màrààrún
six	méfà	méfàméfà		èèméfà	méfèèfà
seven	méje	méjeméje		èèméje	méjèèje
eight	méjo	méjoméjo		èèméjo	méjèèjo
nine	mésán	mésánmésán		èèmésán	mésèèsán
ten	méwá	méwáméwá		èèmèwá	méwèèwá
twenty	ogún	ogogún		igbà ogún	gbogbo ogún
thirty	ògbòn	ògbògbòn		igbà ògbòn	gbogbo ògbòn
one hundred	ògórùn	ògògórùn		igbà ògórùn	gbogbo ògórùn

- He beats me twice → *Wón lù mí lèèméjì*

Fig. 1: Schema for X-bar theory

- His ten books → *Ìwé rẹ̀ méwèèwá*
- When the number precedes a noun without being preceded by any of the words mentioned in (1) and the noun is succeeded by the word “each” or the number takes a plural form, e.g., ‘twos’, it is translated into the adverb of number form. e.g.
 - Two eggs each → *Èyìn méjíméjì*
 - Line the boys up in twos → *Tò àwọn omòdékúnrin náà sí ilà ní méjíméjì*
 - when the number precedes a noun without being preceded by any of the words mentioned in (1) and the noun is not succeeded by the word “each”, it is translated into the adjectival form. e.g.
 - Two eggs → *Èyìn méjì*
 - Ade gave Tolu seven books → *Adé fún Tolú ní ìwé méje*
 - when the number is succeeded by the word “times” or is in the form once, twice, or trice, it is translated into the adverb of time form. e.g.

B. Grammar formulation

The English phrases considered here are verbal phrases and nominal phrases. Since the linguistic machine translation process involves the grammar of both the source and target language, the rewrite rule of the grammars are formulated using the X-Bar theory. One for English - the source, other for Yorùbá - the target language. The production rule of grammar is defined in Definition 3.1:

Definition 3.1

$$G ::= \langle D, T, P, S \rangle \quad (2)$$

- *G* implies the grammar
- *D* implies the non-terminal symbols,
- *T* implies the terminal symbols,
- *P* implies the production rule and
- *S* is the start symbol.

For English grammar, the production rules is as follows:

$$D = \{XP, NP, VP, PP, AdjP, N, V, Det, Adj, Adv, N', V', P\}$$

$$T = \{\text{list of } N, \text{List of } V, \text{List of } Det, \text{list of } P, \text{list of } Adj, \text{list of } Adv\}$$

$$S = \{XP\}$$

$$XP \rightarrow NP \mid VP \quad (3)$$

$$NP \rightarrow DetP N' \mid N \quad (4)$$

$$N' \rightarrow Adj NP \mid NP NP \quad (5)$$

$$VP \rightarrow V' \quad (6)$$

$$V' \rightarrow V' AdvP \mid V' NP \quad (7)$$

$$V' \rightarrow V NP \mid V' PP \quad (8)$$

$$V' \rightarrow NP V \mid V AdvP \quad (9)$$

$$AdvP \rightarrow Adv \quad (10)$$

$$DetP \rightarrow Det \quad (11)$$

$$PP \rightarrow P NP \quad (12)$$

$$Det \rightarrow \text{listof} Det \quad (13)$$

$$N \rightarrow \text{listof}N \quad (14)$$

$$V \rightarrow \text{listof}V \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Adj} \rightarrow \text{listofAdj} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Adv} \rightarrow \text{listofAdv} \quad (17)$$

$$P \rightarrow \text{listof}P \quad (18)$$

Where XP, NP, VP, PP, AdjP, AdvP, DetP, Det, N, V, Adj, Adv, P, N', V' represents X-phrase, noun phrase, verb phrase, prepositional phrase, Adjectival phrase, Adverbial phrase, Determinant phrase, determinant, noun, verb, adjective, possessive noun, adverb, preposition, N-bar and V-bar respectively. The Yorùbá output grammar is also shown in the grammar production rule defined in Definition 3.2 :

$$G ::= \langle D, T, P, S \rangle \quad (19)$$

- G implies the grammar,
- D implies the non-terminal symbols,
- P implies the terminal symbols and
- S is the start symbol.

For Yorùbá grammar, the production rules is as follows:

$$D = \{XP, NP, VP, N, V, Det, Adj, Adv, N', V', P\}$$

$$P = \{\text{list of } N, \text{List of } V, \text{List of } Det, \text{list of } P, \text{list of } Adj, \text{list of } Adv\}$$

$$S = XP$$

$$XP \rightarrow NP \mid VP \quad (20)$$

$$NP \rightarrow N' \mid N \mid N' DetP \quad (21)$$

$$NP \rightarrow N' AdjP \mid DetP N' \quad (22)$$

$$VP \rightarrow V' \quad (23)$$

$$N' \rightarrow NP Adj \mid NP NP \quad (24)$$

$$V' \rightarrow V NP \mid V' Adv \quad (25)$$

$$V' \rightarrow V' NP \mid V Adv \quad (26)$$

$$V' \rightarrow V' V \mid NP V \quad (27)$$

$$DetP \rightarrow Det \quad (28)$$

$$Det \rightarrow \text{listof}Det \quad (29)$$

$$N \rightarrow \text{listof}N \quad (30)$$

$$V \rightarrow \text{listof}V \quad (31)$$

$$Adj \rightarrow \text{listof}Adj \quad (32)$$

$$Adv \rightarrow \text{listof}Adv \quad (33)$$

$$P \rightarrow \text{listof}P \quad (34)$$

Where S, NP, VP, DetP, Det, N, V, Adj, Adv, P, N', and V' represents phrase, noun phrase, verb phrase, determinant phrase, determinant, noun, verb, adjective, possessive noun, pronoun, possessive pronoun, adverb, preposition, N-bar, and V-bar, respectively.

The parse trees for the English text and corresponding Yorùbá text, the grammars produced for the adjectival form are shown in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. Figures 3a and 4a show the parse tree produced for two instances of adverb of number form for English, while Figures 3b and 4b shows the tree for their Yorùbá translations. Figures 5a and 6a show the parse tree produced for two instances of adverb of time form for English, while Figures 5b and 6b show the tree for their Yorùbá translations. Figures 7a and 7b

show the produced tree for the English text and Yorùbá text of the all-form, respectively.

C. System Description

A conceptual model for the translation process of the system is shown in Figure 8 and involves some techniques. These techniques include tokenising the input phrase and extracting the English number text from the simple English phrase. In this process, the input phrase is broken down into chunks called tokens, and the number text in the phrase is extracted. In the second process, the extracted number text is then converted to the Hindu-Arabic digit equivalent. In the third process, the phrase is parsed using English grammar, and the form of the number is determined (adjective, noun, adverb of number, or adverb of time) in the fourth process. The phrase is then translated into the Yorùbá form in the fifth process.

In the entire model, the system takes in an English language phrase containing a number of texts and outputs the corresponding translation in the traditional Yorùbá language.

The processes of the model are further broken down in the subsections below.

1) Tokenization and textual number identification

This process is performed when the phrase is inputted. Here the phrase is broken down into tokens of words. Each word is compared with the dictionary of number text, and the number word token found is stacked for further processing. For example, the sentence:

“Ade gave her five thousand seven hundred and fifty naira.”

was broken into tokens:

“Ade, gave, her, five, thousand, seven, hundred, and, fifty, naira”

and the number words:

“five, thousand, seven, hundred, and fifty”

was extracted and catenated to form:

“five thousand seven hundred and fifty.”

The procedure is shown in Algorithm 1

2) Textual number to Hindu-Arabic number

In this process, the textual number is converted to the Hindu-Arabic digit for easy parsing in sentences and decomposition. This process takes the textual number, tokenizes it, and removes the token “and” if it is present in the list of tokens in between numbers. It then represents each token with its corresponding digit.

For example, the list of tokens: [five, thousand, seven, hundred, and, fifty] becomes [5, 1000, 7, 100, 50] which is further reduced to [5000, 700, 50], these are added together to form the Arabic digit 5750, which is the number equivalent to the text. The procedure for this is shown in Algorithm 2. After the conversion of the text to a digit, the number text within the original phrase is replaced with the

generated Hindu-Arabic digit. The reason for this is to be able to relate to the number and its surrounding text. In doing that, the sentence above becomes:

“Ade gave her 5750 naira”

which, when tagged, becomes:

“Ade(Noun) gave(Verb) her(Pronoun) 5750 Naira(Noun)”

3) Number context determination

This process involves considering words around the number and how they affect it. This may involve the part of speech of the words before and after the number. For example, if the word that follows the number is a noun, the number is likely to be an adjective qualifying the noun. The number may be an adverb qualifying a verb. The number can also be followed by an “s” e.g., twos, tens, hundreds, or thousands. When the article “the” or the word “all” precedes a number, the number is a compound noun. From the sentence:

Ade gave her 5750 Naira.

the number 5750 qualifies the Noun ‘Naira’, which makes the number an adjective.

4) Text translation to Yorùbá form

In this process, the number decomposition is done, after which linguistic rules are applied based on the form of the number. The remaining English text is translated to Yorùbá text and the Yorùbá text for the number is inserted into the text to replace the number digit. In this process, the number 5750, known to be an adjective, was translated to the adjectival form of the Yorùbá numeral.

1) Number Decomposition

The essence of number decomposition is to break a number into smaller units to represent the number phrase effectively. [6, 7, 22, 23], explained how the Yorùbá numerals could be represented in vigesimal (base 20). The first of the processes is to generate the magnitude stack from the given number. The number is decomposed into five possible units: d_0 , d_1 , d_2 , d_3 , and d_4 .

where:

1. d_0 is a number from 0 to 9, i.e., an element of the set $DIGIT = \{0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9\}$.
2. d_1 is 0 or a multiple of 20, i.e. ($d_1 = 20 \times n | 0 \leq n < 10$) or reducing the multiple of 20 by 10, i.e. ($d_1 = (20 \times n) - 10 | 2 \leq n \leq 10$).

3. d_2 is 0 or a multiple of 200, i.e. ($d_2 = 200 \times n | 0 \leq n < 10$) or reducing the multiple of 200 by 100, i.e. ($d_2 = (200 \times n) - 100 | 2 \leq n \leq 10$).
4. d_3 is 0 or a multiple of 2,000, i.e. ($d_3 = 2,000 \times n | 0 \leq n < 10$) or reducing the multiple of 2000 by 1000, i.e. ($d_3 = ((2,000 \times n) - 1000) | 2 \leq n \leq 10$).
5. d_4 is 0 or multiple of 20,000 i.e. ($d_4 = 20,000 \times n | 0 \leq n < \infty$).

The addition of these units makes up the number i.e. number = $d_0 + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4$

The example for some numbers are shown below

$86 = [d_4, d_3, d_2, d_1, d_0] = [0, 0, 0, 80, 6]$

$2389 = [d_4, d_3, d_2, d_1, d_0] = [0, 2000, 300, 80, 9]$

$123947 = [d_4, d_3, d_2, d_1, d_0] = [120000, 3000, 900, 40, 7]$

In the magnitude stack, the zeros are eliminated.

This makes the units of the number above:

$86 = [80, 6]$

$2389 = [2000, 300, 80, 9]$

$123947 = [120000, 3000, 900, 40, 7]$

Algorithm 3 for number decomposition was adapted from [7].

2) Linguistic rules application

Some linguistic rules were applied to translate the number text to the respective forms. The details of the process for each form are described below.

1. Adjectival form

The adjectival form of the Yorùbá numeral takes the simple short form of the Yorùbá numeral in the form *òkan*, *èjì*, *èta*, etc.

The *ò* in *òkan* is removed while all the numbers that are prefixed with *èjì* to *èwá* are prefixed by “m” and the vowel starting the number is changed from low tone to high tone, and every other number of the multiples of 10 retains there name.

2. Adverb of Number form

The formation of the adverb of number form is done by duplicating numbers from two to ten, duplicating the first two letters of the multiples of twenty till 180, prefixing the numbers starting with *àád* and *èéd* with *àr* and *èr* respectively.

Fig. 1: (a) Parse tree “give tolu ten eggs”. (b) Translation parse tree for “give tolu ten eggs”.

Fig. 2: (a) Parse tree for “group them in tens”. (b) Translation parse tree for “group them in tens”

Fig. 4: (a) Parse tree “give them five hundred eggs each”. (b) Translation parse tree for “give them five hundred eggs each”.

Fig. 3: (a) Parse tree for “teach tolu five times”. (b) Translation parse tree for “teach tolu five times”

Fig. 4: (a) Parse tree for “teach Tolu twice”. Translation parse tree for “teach Tolu twice”.

Fig. 5: (a) Parse tree for “the five eggs”. (b) Translation parse tree for “the five eggs”.

Fig. 6: Translation system for English number text in context to Yorùbá

Algorithm 1 Textual Number Identification

```

1: Input: sentence
2: Output: English Number Text
3: procedure getNumberFromSentence(sentence)
4:     num = [];
5:     denwords = sentence.replace('-', '').split()
6:     for i in denwords do
7:         if (i in NumberWordArray) or (i == 'and') then
8:             num.add(i)
9:         end if
10:    end for
11:    numberSentence = "".join(num)
12:    return numberSentence
13: end procedure

```

Algorithm 2 Textual Number to Hindu-Arabic Number

```

1: Input: numberSentence
2: Output: Number
3: Procedure tokenizeNumber(numberSentence)
4:     words = numberSentence.split()
5:     return (|SingleWordNumber(i)| for i in words) if (i != "and")
6: end procedure
7: input: numbertokens
8: output: tokens
9: procedure COALESCETOKENS(TOKENS)
10:    result = []
11:    for token in tokens do
12:        if result and token == 100 and result[-1] < 100 then
13:            result[-1] *= 100
14:        else if result and result[-1] < 1000 and token < 1000 then
15:            result[-1] += token
16:        else
17:            result.append(token)
18:        return result
19:    end procedure
20: Input: tokens
21: Output: Number
22: procedure PARSE(TOKENS)
23:    Number = 0
24:    while tokens do
25:        if tokens.length == 1 or tokens[0] ≥ 1000 then
26:            total += tokens.pop(0)
27:        else
28:            assert tokens[1] ≥ 1000
29:            total += tokens[0] * tokens[1]
30:            del tokens[:2]
31:        end if
32:    end while
33: end procedure

```

3. Adverb of Time form

The formation of the adverb of time form is done by adding a prefix of *èè* to the adjectival form of numbers such as one and every other number that starts with an "m". Every other number that is multiple of 10 is preceded by the word *ìgbà*.

4. All-form

The formation of the all-form is done by inserting the consonant starting the second syllable, and the vowel ending the first syllable with the low tone changed to high. This occurs for *Yorùbá* adjectival numbers starting with "m" excluding fifteen because

the second syllable is a vowel and not a set of letters starting with a consonant. Other multiples of ten are preceded by the word *gbogbo*.

D. System design

The design of this system was done using UML diagrams: Activity diagram, sequence diagram, and class diagram. The pseudocode for the system is shown in Algorithm 4. For the system to be implemented using the Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) approach, a class diagram comprising 5 classes was designed. The pictorial relationship between the classes is shown in the class diagram in Figure 9.

E. System Implementation

The system was implemented using Python programming language, and Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) was used to implement the system.

IV. RESULTS

The developed system gives the phrasal *Yorùbá* translation of the English phrase containing number text and the word-for-word translation.

The *Yorùbá* phrasal output of the software for selected phrases is described in this section.

The following phrases were used as inputs to test the system.

1. The five eggs
2. Teach tolu five times
3. Teach tolu twice
4. Give Tolu ten eggs
5. Group them in tens
6. Give them five hundred eggs each

A. Word-for-word translation

The system takes a phrase and gives the translation without considering the grammar of the language. The number of phrases is simply translated to the adjectival form, and context is not considered.

For example:

1. "The five eggs" is translated to *náà máàrùn-ún eyin*.
2. "Teach tolu five times" is translated to "*kò Tolù m̀árùn-ún igb̀à*"
3. "Teach tolu twice" is translated to "*kò Tolù méjì igb̀à*"
4. "give tolu ten eggs" is translated to "*fún Tolù m̀ewàá eyin*"
5. "group them in tens" is translated to *tò wòn ní m̀ewàá*.
6. "give them five hundred eggs each" is translated to *fún wòn è̀dè̀gb̀eta eyin kò̀òkan*.

These outputs can be seen on the word-for-word translation text box in Figures 10a, 10b, 11a, 11b, 12a, 12b.

B. Phrasal output and parse trees

The rule of grammar for both languages is considered when translating the number phrase from English to *Yorùbá*.

1. "The five eggs" is translated to *eyin máàrùn-ún náà*.
 2. "Teach tolu five times" is translated to "*kò Tolù l̀è̀m̀árùn-ún*"
 3. "Teach tolu twice" is translated to "*kò Tolù l̀è̀m̀éjì*"
 4. "give tolu ten eggs" is translated to "*fún Tolù ní eyin m̀ewàá*"
 5. "group them in tens" is translated to *tò wòn ní m̀ewàám̀ewàá*.
 6. "give them five hundred eggs each" is translated to "*fún wòn ní eyin è̀r̀è̀dè̀gb̀eta*".
- which are demonstrated in Figures 10a, 10b, 11a, 11b, 12a and 12b.

Algorithm 3 Magnitude generator algorithm

```

1: Input: number
2: Output: magnitudeStack
3: procedure generateMagnitude(number)
4:    $d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4 = 0$ 
5:    $divisor = 10$ 
6:    $magnitudeStack = []$ 
7:   while number  $\neq 0$  do
8:      $remainder = number \% divisor$ 
9:     if remainder  $\neq 0$  then
10:       $magnitudeStack.push(remainder)$ 
11:    end if
12:     $number = number - remainder$ 
13:     $divisor = divisor \times 10$ 
14:  end
15:  for mag in magnitudeStack do
16:    if mag < 10 then
17:       $d_0 = d_0 + mag$ 
18:    else if mag < 200 then
19:       $d_1 = d_1 + mag$ 
20:    else if mag < 2000 then
21:       $d_2 = d_2 + mag$ 
22:    else if mag < 20000 then
23:       $d_3 = d_3 + mag$ 
24:    else
25:       $d_4 = d_4 + mag - (mag \% 20000)$ 
26:       $d_3 = d_3 + (mag \% 20000)$ 
27:    end if
28:  end
29:   $magnitudeStack = [d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4]$ 
30:  return magnitudeStack.reverse()
31: end procedure

```

Algorithm 4 Algorithm of the translation system

- 1: **Input:** English number phrase
- 2: **Output:** Yoruba phrase
- 3: **procedure** START
- 4: input phrase
- 5: **if** number in phrase **then**
- 6: Extract number text
- 7: Convert number text to Hindu-Arabic Digit
- 8: Replace number text in sentence with digit
- 9: Parse sentence using English grammar
- 10: Translate number to Yoruba based on it's contextual form
- 11: Output Yoruba phrase
- 12: Stop
- 13: **else**
- 14: Stop
- 15: **end procedure**

V. EVALUATION OF THE SYSTEM

The evaluation of the system was done by comparing the system's output with the translation of an expert. The reference serves as the reference, while the system serves as the candidate. There were 20 phrases in all; 5 phrases to cover the adjectival form, 5 phrases to cover the adverb of number form, 5 phrases to cover the adverb of time form, 5 phrases to cover the 'all' form, of which 5 cover the usage of the word 'the' before the number text, and 5 covers the usage of the word 'all' before the number text.

The BLEU score was generated using the Python programming language module for calculating the BLEU score. The cumulative score for unigram, bigram, and trigram was generated, and the average for each form of number phrases was presented in Table II. From this evaluation, it was discovered that the system has a higher precision of 0.946, 0.948, and 0.902 in translating the adjectival, adverb of number, and adverb of time number phrases and an average precision of 0.534 in translating all-form number phrases.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, it has been shown that a number in a statement made in the English language has a different form in which it can be translated into the Yorùbá language, depending on the context in which the number is used. The processes involved in the translation of the English number text in context to the various Yorùbá forms are Tokenization and textual number identification, Textual number to Hindu-Arabic number, Number context determination, Text translation to Yorùbá form, Number Decomposition, and Linguistic rules application. The work started by identifying the structure of the English numeral text to be translated

from and the Yorùbá sentences we are translating to. Then, the work designed Context-Free Grammars that capture the source and target languages. Furthermore, the work implemented software to convert the source numeral sentence to the target language and draw the parse trees for both languages.

In addition, the work carried out the study and analysis of the Yorùbá numerals with a focus on extracting the knowledge needed and the conditions required for the translation into different forms from an English phrase based on context.

We discussed the phrasal context of the numbers in English and how they are translated to the corresponding Yorùbá text.

We have presented a grammar capturing the English phrase and a Push Down Automaton for recognition. The processes involved in the translation have been discussed. The results of the study have been presented and discussed to provide an insight into the contextual translation of the Yorùbá numeral and call attention to the traditional level of Yorùbá numeral text. In this study,

1. we found out that there are various forms of the Yorùbá numeral text, and they have their peculiarities, such as: how they are formed, how they are translated from the English phrasal context, and the linguistic rules involved in their pronunciation.
2. the software developed was able to give 100% accuracy on tested data.

The result of this study has applications in Machine Translation. In any English to Yorùbá Machine Translation system, for an English phrase or sentence containing number text, the context in which the text appears must be taken into consideration before translation. So the system developed can be implemented as a sub-system of a full English to Yorùbá Machine Translation system. Certain concepts are closely related to this research area that we could not explore in this study. We are pointing out this area so that researchers can be drawn to them.

Fig. 9: System's class diagram

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10: (a) Translation for “the five eggs” (b) Translation for “teach tolu five times”

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11: (a) Translation for “teach tolu twice” (b) Translation for “give tolu ten eggs”

(a)

(b)

Fig. 12: (a) Translation for “group them in tens” (b) Translation for “give them five hundred eggs each”

TABLE II. EVALUATION RESULT

Forms	Adjectival	Adverb of number	Adverb of time	All-form
Score	0.946	0.948	0.902	0.534

There is a need to research the translation of cardinal numbers from one indigenous language in Nigeria to the other. There is also a need to research the usage of Yorùbá number text in arithmetic to aid the usage of the language to teach mathematics in school. In so doing, areas like currency, percentage, ratio, date, and time must be covered.

In this research, we have explored the different forms of the Yorùbá numeral (Simple Enumeration, Numismatics, Adjective, Adverb of time, Adverb of numbers, and all-forms). This work will help improve the frontiers of machine translation from the English language to the Yorùbá language, as a numeral is an essential aspect of any language. This work's phonological aspect will also help push the frontiers of the text-to-speech (TTS) system for the Yorùbá language. This will help to understand the full pattern of speech sounds for the Yorùbá numeral system. The work does not consider number ambiguity in the Yorùbá text.

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